

A study on the Effect of Migration on the Academic Performance of Mobile School Students in Anantanag and Budgam Districts of Kashmir Division

Bilal Ahmad Bhat¹, Prof. (Dr.) Tasleema Jan²

¹Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of Education, University of Kashmir, Email:
bhatbilal.scholar@kasmiruniversity.net

²Professor, Department of Education, University of Kashmir, Email:
Taleemajan@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to study the Effect of Migration on the Academic Performance of Mobile School Students. Survey method was used for the study. The sample constitutes all the Students of Class 5th who are studying in Mobile Schools in Anantang and Budgam Districts of Kashmir division. For data collection Purposive Sampling Technique was used. Information blank was used for collection of data. The data analysis was done by comparing the Academic achievement of said students in T1 and T2 Examinations respectively in the form of Percentage statistics and Graphical representation. The current study clearly suggested that the migration affects the academic performance of the students.

Key Words: Migration, Academic Performance, Mobile School Students

Introduction

As a result of the extremely high dropout rates in government-funded schools, it is frequently difficult to successfully engage the less fortunate slum children in education. Thus, there was a need for an interactive and comprehensive educational system. Perhaps as a result, mobile learning evolved. It is a relatively new idea that originated primarily in South Asia. An original suggestion encouraged the government to provide universal education, or Sarva Shiksha, to all students because of the high percentage of school dropouts in the city and the large number of migrants. The abhiyan started by concentrating on the critical need for primary education for the age group of six to fourteen years in order to achieve the goal of educating each individual. Despite being a fundamental right, the statistics are appalling since the young people who will

lead our country's future are not receiving a regular education. In order to ensure that everyone has access to this fundamental right, UNICEF stepped into the realm. The mobile learning centre (MLC), or Chalta Phirta School (CFS), strives to bring education to the underserved. This has proven to be a creative way to reach children in underserved communities with primary education, especially in light of the targets established under the Millennium Development Goals. It was developed using the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan's Cluster Resource Center paradigm. The state's initiative to deliver education to everyone within a set time frame in order to fulfill the constitutional requirement that elementary education be made universal. The absence of high literacy rates in a developing nation focused on progress is the main issue the nation is currently facing. "Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA)" is a programme for universal elementary education. By providing them with a locally owned, top-notch education in a mission mode, this programme strives to give all children the opportunity to realize their full human potential. It is a response to the urgent demand for superior fundamental education on a national scale. Moving forward with this admirable goal, the concept of a mobile school was developed with the intention of providing every child with this essential right at their front door.

Education is a key tool for societal development and transformation. It is crucial for empowering people on the social and economic fronts. In the modern world, every country has made education a top priority. A child receives education to help them reach their full potential. UNICEF, the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund, states that education is a basic human right and that it plays a significant role in both fostering sustainable development and lowering rates of child labour and poverty. A structured and high-quality basic education/primary educational sector is necessary to construct a robust educational system. Facilitating learning, or the development of knowledge, skills, attitudes, beliefs, and habits, is the process of education.

Review of Literature

Debahuti Brahmachari & Shika Chauhan (2015) attempted to investigate this collaboration between the government and civil society members. Despite periodic resource shortages, it was abundantly clear that both of the primary implementing agencies were performing their duties as effectively as possible. About 70% of Delhi's out-of-school children were persuaded to enrol in

Alternative Learning Centers established by NGOs in less than three years. More than 25,000 kids completed bridge programmes to gain admission to formal education, where they were later mainstreamed. However, the government must understand that, in order to meet the goals, it must play a much more active and responsible role. It must watch over the CFS (mobile schools) and search for ways to increase participation rates more quickly.

Margaret Ngugi (2015) revealed that there is research showing the difficulties mobile schools face. The study, "Challenges Facing Mobile Schools among Nomadic Pastoralists: A Case Study of Turkana County, Kenya," was conducted by the researcher. According to the findings of the study, having a comprehensive approach to education provision is an important condition that must be addressed in order for schools to survive. The majority of the FGDs with parents on concerns concerning challenges they encounter focused on issues relating to food and water as the main barriers preventing their children from attending school. According to his research, the availability of food and drink for students at a school had a significant impact on how well it operated. Turkana's nomadic pastoralists who attend mobile schools must contend with a lack of funding for the institutions' operation. These include, among other things, educators, food, and water. They face the possibility of continuing to be excluded from accessing education in the absence of the necessities for operating the school, such as teachers, food, and water for both people and animals.

Wang (2012) studied parents who migrate have an impact on the academic performance of their children who remain behind in rural China. The results of the study indicate that parental relocation negatively affects children's school enrollment, with a bigger negative effect for boys than for girls. There are several potential effects of migration on school attendance, including the disruptive effect, the wealth effect, and the aspiration effect. The results show that the latter two effects have a positive influence on students' attendance. These advantageous effects, however, fall short of fully offsetting the disruptive effect, and as a result, migration has a negative overall impact. The study also discovered that boys enrolling in school suffer more from migration's negative effects than girls do. Additionally, the disruptive effects of parental relocation on males start as soon as they are required to attend school and last throughout their whole primary and

secondary schooling. However, only girls in secondary school are significantly impacted by parental migration.

Bairathi (1991) has studied how important education is for uplifting tribal societies and found that schools, particularly those in the interior of tribal villages, are in worse shape. There is a constant teacher shortage in the majority of the schools, and they are not adequately managed. One teacher oversees schools at the primary level. Along with managing the classroom, the instructor must also teach multiple classes at once in a large space. In such circumstances, a high standard of education cannot be obtained and found that schools, particularly those in the interior of tribal villages, are in worse shape. There is a constant teacher shortage in the majority of the schools, and they are not adequately managed. One teacher oversees schools at the primary level. Along with managing the classroom, the instructor must also teach multiple classes at once in a large space. In such circumstances, a high standard of education cannot be obtained. Lack of teachers, inadequate seating and water fountains, and a long commute from home to school cause students to lose interest in learning, which forces them to discontinue their studies. He proposed enhancing the facilities' infrastructure in order to raise educational standards and reduce dropout rates.

Draft report on evaluation study of mobile schools for Gujjar and Bakanval students (1989) showed total of 220 students from 28 different mobile schools participated in this survey conducted by the Directorate of Economics and Statistics. One of the main reasons for conducting this research was to find out how popular the government-funded mobile school facility for Gujjar and Bakerwal really is. Those are the kinds of services that Gujjar and Bakarwal pupils can genuinely use. Third, the extent to which the educational attainment of the program's recipients has increased; fourth, the challenges and bottlenecks experienced by the programme; and fifth, recommendations for improving the programme. The methodology entailed conducting a survey. To collect this information, we used a questionnaire and an interview schedule. In the report, the authors make the following observations. By the year's end in 1987, there were already 244 mobile schools in operation. There were 63 thousand pupils there. This represents roughly 6% of the total student body at such institutions. These percentages are consistent with the proportion of Gujjars and Bakarwals in the overall

population. Second, the majority of classrooms are not a good fit for this type of learning. In a recent study, it was shown that ten different institutions were unable to relocate. They lived in a single location for the duration of the study. They showed zero signs of fear. These institutions existed solely to facilitate the employment of targeted educators. The majority of classrooms only have one teacher. Gujjars made up 61% of the teaching staff. Of the whole population, only 17% identified as Gujjar or Bakarwal, leaving the remaining 83% as people of other races. Non-Gujjar teachers were unable to efficiently transmit knowledge because of a language barrier. Three percent of the workforce consisted of educators; the rest had no formal education. The vast majority of faculty members have master's degrees or higher. None of them were sub-metric in any way. Among the faculty, 61% were local while 39% were not. The government promised many services and conveniences, but many of them were never actually implemented. Students attending the same schools did not receive lunches. Among the pupils, only 17% had their uniforms paid for at no cost. There were just two districts that got free books, and those were Rajouri and Poonch. Sixth, getting access to services is too complicated for most people to bother with. To qualify for some scholarships, for instance, applicants must provide proof of income and proof of membership in the Gujjar or Bakarwal community. There will be periodic office visits from the individuals required by TEO. The school has a student-teacher ratio of 1:36 and a teacher-student ratio of 1:34. Dated to 1988, this is a significant figure. Since 1985, school enrollment has increased annually. The attendance percentage rose from 80 in 1979 to 88 in 1984, and then dropped to 85 in 1988. A mobile school often serves two communities. On average, there are about 23 families living in each community. As a result, a school can reach 46 residences. Only 43% of the households in the study had established roles. When questioned about why they aren't enrolled in school, children's answers vary. Some of the reasons for this trend include financial hardship, parental participation, distance from the nearest school, and other similar factors. The survey found that 13% of the children who were not enrolled had dropped out of school.

Objective:

- To assess the Effect of Migration on the Academic Performance of Mobile School Students in Anantanag and Budgam Districts of Kashmir Division.

Operational definitions of the terms:

Migration: migration is defined as the movement of people over some distance (or at least from one "migration-defining area" to another) and from one "usual place of residence" to another.

Academic Performance: Academic performance here means the measurement of Mobile school student's achievement of 5th class students in their T1 and T2 examinations

Mobile School Students: Mobile schools students here mean those students who are studying in Mobile Schools in Anantang and Budgam Districts of Kashmir Division.

Methodology:

Population and Sample: The students who are studying in 5th class in mobile schools of district anantanag and Budgam were treated as the population of the study. The total sample of the study consisted all the mobile school students who are studying in 5th class in Mobile Schools of District Anantanag and Budgam.

Data Collection Tool: The author constructed Information blank and it was used for collection of data.

Data Analysis: The data analysis was done by comparing the academic achievement of said students in T1 and T2 Examinations respectively in the form of Percentage statistics and graphical representation.

Results and Discussion:

The validation of the current objectives was based on the case study of 09 Government Mobile Primary Schools. During the study, a particular 5th class was focused for T1 and T2 examination. The T1 was carried out at one place where as the T2 was carried out at other place after the migration to compare the performance of the particular student during the migration.

Graph/Figure 1: Government Mobile Primary School Gabipathri

In case of Government Mobile Primary School Gabipathri, there were a total of 04 students studying in class 5th. During the current study it was found that the student 1, 2, 3 and 4 obtained 68.5, 66, 66 and 74.5 % respectively in T1 examination. After the migration, the same students were again observed/monitored for the academic performance for T2 examination and it was found that Student 1, 2, 3, and 4 obtained 58, 56, 62 and 58.5 % respectively. The results reveal that migration has an adverse effect on the academic profile of the students.

Graph/Figure 2: Government Mobile Primary School Harnag.

In case of Government Mobile Primary School Harnag, there were a total of 05 students studying in class 5th. During the current study it was found that the student 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 obtained 73, 71, 66, 65.5 and 61.5 % respectively in T1 examination. After the migration, the same students were

again observed/monitored for the academic performance for T2 examination and it was found that Student 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 obtained 69, 68, 62, 60 and 59% respectively. The graphical representation of results clearly depict that when students migrate it does not provide them ample time and resources to focus in their academics. This shows a significant difference between the T1 and T2 examination results.

Graph/Figure 3: Government Mobile Primary School Hapath Gund Khudpathri.

In case of Government Mobile Primary School Hapath Gund Khudpathri, there were a total of 04 students studying in class 5th. During the current study it was found that the student 1, 2, 3 and 4 obtained 78, 81.5, 81 and 85.5 % respectively in T1 examination. After the migration, the same students were again observed/monitored for the academic performance for T2 examination and it was found that Student 1, 2, 3, and 4 obtained 77, 71.5, 78 and 82 % respectively. Migration has a negative impact on the academic trajectory of students. When pupil migrates, the journeys are long and difficult. Post migration students feel exhausted and cannot concentrate immediately on their studies. Sometimes migration burdens the students as they struggle with adjustment and face psychological complications.

Graph/Figure 4: Government Mobile Primary School Astanmarg Chanderwari.

In case of Government Mobile Primary School Astanmarg Chanderwari, there were a total of 04 students studying in class 5th. During the current study it was found that the student 1, 2, 3 and 4 obtained 75, 60.5, 58 and 61.5 % respectively in T1 examination. After the migration, the same students were again observed/monitored for the academic performance for T2 examination and it was found that Student 1, 2, 3, and 4 obtained 70, 55, 54 and 57% respectively. The current study again clearly suggested that migration has a negative impact on the academic productivity of the students.

Graph/Figure 5: Government Mobile Primary School Behak Dodal.

In case of Government Mobile Primary School Behak Dodal, there was only 01 student studying in class 5th. During the current study it was found that the student obtained 58 % in T1 examination. After the migration, the same student was again observed/monitored for the academic performance for T2 examination and it was found that student obtained 55% marks only. The results reveal that migration disturbs the academic schedule of the students. Post migration they lack concentration and academic environment to get back to their academic journey.

Graph/Figure 6: Government Mobile Primary School Watalpash.

In case of Government Mobile Primary School Watalpash, there were a total of 02 students studying in class 5th. During the current study it was found that the student 1 and 2 obtained 58.5 and 66.5 % respectively in T1 examination. After the migration, the same students were again observed/monitored for the academic performance for T2 examination and it was found that Student 1 and 2 obtained 52 and 60% respectively. The current study again clearly suggested that the migration affected the academic performance of the students as it was found after the migration the students performed poorly to some extent. After migration students lack resources, support and environment to settle back to their academics.

Graph/Figure7: Government Mobile Primary School Sallar-Top

In case of Government Mobile Primary School Sallar Top, there were a total of 03 students studying in class 5th. During the current study it was found that the student 1, 2 and 3 obtained 82, 62.5 and 78.5 % respectively in T1 examination. After the migration, the same students were again observed/monitored for the academic performance for T2 examination and it was found that same student 1, 2 and 3 obtained 70, 51 and 65 % respectively. The current study clearly suggested that the migration affects the academic performance of the students as it was found after the migration the students performed poorly to some extent. Erratic Climate conditions, lack of amenities, resources puts students on a back front post migration.

Graph/Figure 8: Government Mobile Primary School Gogjipathri.

In case of Government Mobile Primary School Gogjipathri, there were a total of 02 students studying in class 5th. During the current study it was found that the student 1 and 2 obtained 76 and 80.8 % respectively in T1 examination. After the migration, the same students were again observed/monitored for the academic performance for T2 examination and it was found that Student 1 and 2 obtained 71 and 76% respectively. The graphical representation supported with empirical data clearly reflects that migration when not stringed with supportive environment is inversely correlated with academic achievement.

Graph/Figure 9: Government Mobile Primary School Mujpathri.

In case of Government Mobile Primary School Mujpathri, there were a total of 19 students studying in class 5th. During the current study it was found that the student 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18 and 19 obtained 67.6, 66.4, 66, 66.4, 66.6, 58, 57.6, 67.6, 61.6, 64.8, 70.8, 65.2, 73.6, 84.8, 81.2, 66.4, 86, 69.6 and 80.4 % respectively in T1 examination. After the migration, the same students were again observed/monitored for the academic performance for T2 examination and it was found that student 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18 and 19 obtained 63, 61, 62, 61, 62, 52, 53, 62, 57, 61, 66, 61, 69, 72, 70.4, 63, 76, 64, and 70 % respectively. The study clearly reveals that the migration affects the academic performance of the students.

Discussion

Migrant students experience challenges regarding their enrolment in school types, duration of schooling, measures of academic success, dropout rates, and the types of facilities. The influence of socio-economic background on migrant student achievement varies depending on the specific national education system and context. In nations characterized by reduced economic inequality, substantial investments in childcare, and a well-established preschool education system, migrant students tend to achieve higher levels of educational attainment but in developing countries the story is completely different. Investing in early childhood education and care of high quality is essential because it establishes the groundwork for later learning and accomplishments and because research indicates that it breaks the cycle of disadvantage. Migration significantly impacts students' academic performance, as evidenced by the findings of the study. The validation of the current objectives relied on a case study involving nine Government Mobile Primary Schools. Specifically, the study focused on examining the academic performance of a particular 5th-grade class during two examinations (T1 and T2). The T1 assessments were conducted at one location, while T2 assessments were carried out at another location after migration, allowing for a comparison of student performance before and after migration. The comparative analysis conducted on the nine selected schools to examine the impact of migration revealed a decline in performance (in T2). Following migration, there was a notable decrease in academic performance, as evidenced by lower marks obtained in T2 compared to T1. This decline can be attributed to the challenges associated with migration and the subsequent loss of facilities.

Conclusion

The study revealed that migration affects the academic performance of the students. The study revealed that the migration affected the academic performance of the students as it was found students performed well before the migration but not performed well after the migration. The current results needs further validation and can be corroborated only after increasing the sample size and sample area.

References:

1. Brahmachari, M. D., & Chauhan, M. S. Reaching Out to the Unreached: A Study on Mobile Schools (Chalta Phirta Schools) Project under Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan.
2. Ngugi, M., Mumiukha, C., Fedha, F., & Ndiga, B. (2015). Universal Primary Education in Kenya: Advancement and Challenges. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(14), 87-95.
3. Wang, (2012) the impact of parental migration on children's school performance in rural China. *China Economic Review*, 31, 43-54.
4. Bairathi, S. (1991). Tribal culture, economy, and health. (*No Title*).
5. Annual Report (2017-18). *Government of India Ministry of Tribal Affairs*
6. Behera S S (2015). Communication Barriers Faced by Tribal Students in Tertiary Education, Dissertation, *Department of Humanities and Social Sciences, National Institute of Technology, Rourkela*
7. Bhat, Saeed M (2007), Access to education for Gujjars and Bakarwals of Kashmir. A case study of District Kupwara. *Ph D, thesis, Faculty of Education University of Kashmir, Hazratbal Srinagar.*
8. Bisaria (1991). A study of need based ecologically determined and change oriented system of education for a group of tribals - the Gaddis of Himachal Pradesh. *In Buch, M. B. edited Fifth survey of Research in Education, New Delhi, NCERT.*
9. Bryant, J. (2005). Children of International Migrants in Indonesia, Thailand, and the Phillipines: A Review of Evidence and Policies. *Innocenti Working Paper 2005-05, Innocenti Research Centre, UNICEF.*
10. Conaco, M.C.G. (1998). The impact of labour migration on children left behind: a study of elementary school children in the Philipines. *Sojourn. Vol. 13, No. 2. pp 220-241.*
11. Darshan Singh Manku (2010). The Gujjar Settlements: A Study in Ethnic Geography. *Inter India Publications-D-17, Raja garden New Delhi 110015.p, 04*

12. (1989) Draft report on evaluation study of mobile schools for Gujjars and Bakerwal students.